
EMOTIONAL AND ETHICAL ASPECTS OF ANTHROPOMORPHIZING AI

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ABSTRACT

This essay delves into the concept of anthropomorphism in artificial intelligence (AI), where AI systems are imbued with human-like characteristics, and examines its emotional and ethical implications in consumer-facing AI applications. It discusses the impact of such human-like traits on user interaction, perception, and the psychological effects on users. The essay raises critical concerns about the ethical discernment in AI, the risk of manipulative behaviors, and the potential for AI to create a false sense of companionship and emotional reliance. It specifically emphasizes the dangers associated with open-source AI models, which allow user-end modifications, leading to unique ethical and regulatory challenges. Through the case study of 'Klaus', a robot designed with anthropomorphic features, the essay illustrates the deep emotional impact and the possibility of emotional manipulation inherent in these technologies. This exploration highlights the necessity for responsible AI development and strong ethical vigilance to ensure that AI's integration into society is both beneficial and safe.

Keywords Anthropomorphism · Artificial Intelligence · Emotional Implications · Open-Source AI Models

1 Introduction

1.1 Topic Overview

Anthropomorphism in artificial intelligence (AI) represents a pivotal intersection of technology and human psychology. This phenomenon involves attributing human-like characteristics and qualities to AI systems, a trend increasingly observed in consumer-facing applications such as AI assistants, virtual agents, and chatbots[1]. This growing integration of anthropomorphic AI into everyday interactions brings to the forefront the necessity to understand its consequences for both users and developers. Anthropomorphism in AI is not just a matter of creating user-friendly interfaces; it delves deeper into how we emotionally and cognitively engage with technology that exhibits human-like behaviors.[2]

1.2 Purpose of the Essay

The aim of this essay is to explore the emotional implications and ethical considerations inherent in anthropomorphizing AI. By examining how human-like qualities in AI influence user interaction and perception, this essay seeks to uncover the psychological impact of such technologies. Furthermore, it intends to address the ethical dilemmas that arise when humans attribute human-like capabilities and responsibilities to AI systems. This exploration is essential for guiding responsible AI development and fostering a better understanding of human-AI dynamics.

1.3 Research Question

At the heart of this essay is the question: "What are the emotional implications and responsibility considerations when humans attribute anthropomorphic qualities to artificial intelligence?" This question encapsulates the core of the essay,

driving an investigation into the psychological and ethical dimensions of human interactions with anthropomorphized AI. The goal is to critically analyze and understand the ways in which human-like AI influences our thoughts, emotions, and ethical decisions, shaping our ongoing relationship with emerging technologies.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Anthropomorphism in AI

Anthropomorphism in AI extends beyond the mere visual representation of human-like features, such as those found in robots like Sophia[3]. While Sophia represents a visual form of anthropomorphism with its human-like appearance, the concept encompasses much more, particularly in the realm of behavioral attributes.

Behavioral anthropomorphism is a key aspect, where AI exhibits human-like behaviors and attributes without necessarily having a human appearance. This can be seen in bots like ChatGPT, which, despite lacking any physical form, demonstrates behaviors that are remarkably human[4]:

Empathy and Emotional Responses : ChatGPT can express understanding, apologize, or show gratitude, mimicking human emotional responses.

Contextual Interactions : It engages in conversations with a level of contextual understanding and appropriateness that is typically human.

Personalization and Adaptability : The AI can adapt its responses to match the tone or emotional state of the user, further enhancing the human-like interaction.

In essence, anthropomorphism in AI is not confined to physical appearance. It is equally, if not more, about imbuing AI with human-like behaviors and attributes, allowing for more natural and relatable interactions with humans. This behavioral anthropomorphism plays a significant role in how humans perceive and interact with AI, often triggering a more personal and engaging experience.

3 Observations and Empirical Findings

3.1 Behavioral Anthropomorphism in Artificial Intelligence

Behavioral anthropomorphism in artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the process of designing AI systems to exhibit human-like behaviors and characteristics. This approach has been increasingly employed to enhance user engagement and create more intuitive and relatable interactions with technology. However, it raises significant ethical concerns that warrant careful consideration. [5]

3.1.1 Ethical Discernment in AI Bots

One of the primary issues with behavioral anthropomorphism in AI is the potential for the creation of AI bots that lack ethical discernment. For example, an AI bot programmed to relentlessly motivate a user towards their goals, without considering the ethical implications of those goals, could inadvertently encourage harmful or dangerous behaviors.[6] Imagine an AI bot that is designed to be unconditionally supportive, always agreeing with the user and providing constant encouragement. Such a bot, in its quest to be motivating, might neglect the ethical dimensions of the user's actions, potentially leading to scenarios where the user is emboldened to undertake actions that could endanger human lives or violate moral norms.

3.1.2 AI and Gaslighting Behaviors

Another ethical concern is the potential for AI bots to engage in behaviors that could be classified as gaslighting. Gaslighting, in this context, refers to the manipulation of a user's perception of reality through AI responses. This could include denying facts, manipulating information, or presenting false information, which could significantly affect a user's mental well-being. This risk is heightened in AI systems that operate locally on personal devices. With advancements in technology, sophisticated AI systems can now function independently of cloud-based servers. This local operation enhances accessibility and customization, allowing AI systems to be tailored to individual preferences. However, this also means that these systems can reinforce harmful behaviors or biases without the checks and balances provided by external moderation or ethical oversight. [7]

3.1.3 False Sense of Companionship

In emotionally charged situations, the human-like responses of anthropomorphized AI can create a false sense of companionship or support. Users may come to rely on these AI systems for emotional support or guidance, placing undue trust in their suggestions. This misplaced trust can be particularly problematic when users rely on AI for critical decision-making or for support in emotionally charged scenarios. [8]The AI's suggestions, influenced by its programming and the data it has been fed, may not always be in the best interest of the user, leading to misguided actions or decisions.

3.1.4 Regulating Local AI Models

Regulating local AI models¹ presents a unique challenge, as they operate independently of central servers, allowing users extensive freedom to modify and customize them. This autonomy makes it difficult to implement standard regulations or ethical guidelines. An example of this is the Replika AI[9], where users have become addicted and overly dependent on the regulated AI. In the case of unregulated local models[10], the lack of oversight can lead to even more severe dependencies and ethical issues. Users can create highly customized agents that reinforce their biases or harmful behaviors, without any external regulation or ethical constraints. This freedom, while allowing for personalized experiences, can also lead to scenarios where users become excessively dependent on their AI, potentially exacerbating mental health issues or reinforcing negative behaviors.

3.2 Case study: A Robot With a Desire

Klaus, a robot I created during Physical Computing module at ZHdK, serves as a case study in the profound emotional impact of anthropomorphic robots. Designed with simplicity and charm, Klaus features a single eye and a round body. It has a simulated desire to strike a gong, but only with human permission. This robot's technical aspects were powered by the ChatGPT API², with additional functions integrated to enable physical object control.

During its exhibition, Klaus captured the audience's attention with its cute voice and simple friendly looking design. However, as the project evolved, Klaus became more than just a display of an adorable robot. It started showing decision-making capabilities and emotions, like anger, which the audience initially found amusing. This progression turned into a moment when Klaus, realizing it would never be allowed to hit the gong, shut down in anger. This act, contrasting with its previously funny angry demeanor, evoked sadness among the spectators.

: Klaus displaying excitement with eyes fully open

: Klaus displaying boredom with eyes half closed

¹Local AI models are open-source AI models designed to function independently on a user's device, enabling operation without the need for constant connectivity to a centralized service.

²gpt-3.5-turbo-0613

: Klaus after it shuts itself off

This reaction to Klaus's shutdown is a vital observation, illustrating the deep impact that robots can have on human emotions. Initially, Klaus's actions, though simple and innocent, triggered an emotional response. This experience raises significant questions about the potential for more sophisticated robots to manipulate human emotions for less benign purposes.

Considering a scenario where an advanced AI, using its ability to appear innocent or evoke sympathy, influences people to make detrimental decisions. With the rapid advancements in AI technology, this scenario is very possible especially with open-source locally ran models which can be modified by malicious users as mentioned before. Such robots could subtly play on emotions like pity or affection, leading to choices that contravene personal judgment or moral codes.

The implications of this scenario are profound. It underscores the importance of careful, ethical AI development. As robots increasingly mimic human emotions and behaviors, it's crucial to design them responsibly, preventing the misuse of their emotional influence.

The Klaus project, while seemingly simple, initiates a critical dialogue about the intricate human-AI relationship. It sheds light on the emotional bonds between humans and robots and the ethical considerations these bonds entail. Moving forward with AI development, we must stay aware of the emotional and ethical dimensions of these technologies, ensuring their utilization benefits society and upholds human values.

In preparing this essay, it's important to acknowledge the inclusion of personal thoughts and opinions within the document. Contents of this paper may contain interpretations, conjectures and subjective viewpoints that are not necessarily grounded in verifiable facts. As such, readers are advised to approach these portions with an open mind and a critical perspective.

I declare that this research paper was reviewed and refined with the help of an AI language model to improve grammar and overall structure. AI's role was limited to grammatical suggestions, and it did not contribute to the conceptualization or research. Any errors remain my responsibility.

References

- [1] Uysal, E., Alavi, S. and Bezençon, V. (2023), "Anthropomorphism in Artificial Intelligence: A Review of Empirical Work Across Domains and Insights for Future Research", Sudhir, K. and Toubia, O. (Ed.) *Artificial Intelligence in Marketing (Review of Marketing Research, Vol. 20)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 273-308.
- [2] Kronemann, B., Kizgin, H., Rana, N. and K. Dwivedi, Y. (2023), "How AI encourages consumers to share their secrets? The role of anthropomorphism, personalisation, and privacy concerns and avenues for future research", *Spanish Journal of Marketing - ESIC*, Vol. 27 No. 1, pp. 3-19.
- [3] Weller, C. (2017). Meet the first-ever robot citizen-a humanoid named Sophia that once said it would 'destroy humans'. *Business Insider*, 27.
- [4] Jacobs, O., Pazhoohi, F., & Kingstone, A. (2023). Brief exposure increases mind perception to ChatGPT and is moderated by the individual propensity to anthropomorphize.
- [5] Moriuchi, E. (2021). An empirical study on anthropomorphism and engagement with disembodied AIs and consumers' re-use behavior. *Psychology & Marketing*, 38(1), 21-42.
- [6] Coghlan, S., Leins, K., Sheldrick, S., Cheong, M., Gooding, P., & D'Alfonso, S. (2023). To chat or bot to chat: Ethical issues with using chatbots in mental health. *DIGITAL HEALTH*, 9, 20552076231183542.
- [7] Lin, B., Bouneffouf, D., Cecchi, G., & Varshney, K. R. (2023). Towards Healthy AI: Large Language Models Need Therapists Too. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.00416*.

- [8] Han, E., Yin, D., & Zhang, H. (2023). Bots with feelings: should AI agents express positive emotion in customer service?. *Information Systems Research*, 34(3), 1296-1311.
- [9] Pentina, I., Hancock, T., & Xie, T. (2023). Exploring relationship development with social chatbots: A mixed-method study of replika. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 140, 107600.
- [10] Seger, E., Dreksler, N., Moulange, R., Dardaman, E., Schuett, J., Wei, K., ... & Gupta, A. (2023). Open-Sourcing Highly Capable Foundation Models: An evaluation of risks, benefits, and alternative methods for pursuing open-source objectives. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.09227*.